

Fiscal Policy Measures and Economic Growth in the West African Sub-Region

Falade Bolanle Samson^{#1}, Modestus Nsonwu^{*2}

[#] *Department of Economics, Veritas University Abuja*

Abstract— This study is on Fiscal measures and economic growth in the West African sub-region (ECOWAS). The study used both time series and cross-sectional data over the period 2001 – 2020 of five selected ECOWAS countries. Because the variables used were not stationary at the same order of integration, the panel autoregressive distributed lag (PARDL) regression analysis of pooled mean group (PMG) was used in estimating the model. Secondary data on the growth rate of Gross Domestic Product (GRGDP), gross national expenditure, tax rate and external debt was obtained from World Bank Database, Central Bank Annual Reports of selected countries and the International Monetary Fund reports. The results show that gross national expenditure has a significant and positive effect on the economic growth rate of the ECOWAS countries. Tax rates and external debt have a significant and negative effect on the economic growth rate of the selected countries. Based on these findings, appropriate government capital expenditure channeled on productive sectors such as education, health, and economic services will boost economic growth in the selected ECOWAS States. Appropriate tax rates and tax base should be reviewed to increase tax revenue necessary to fund government expenditure instead of relying on external borrowing to finance budget deficits in the selected ECOWAS Member States. Governments in this region should source for other means of financing their budget deficits since excessive external borrowing acted as a disincentive to growth in the region in the period under consideration.

Keywords— Fiscal Policy, Economic Growth, PARDL, PMG, MG
JEL Classification: B21, B23, C01, C33

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the objectives that countries try to accomplish through the influence of fiscal and monetary policy is economic stabilization. Taxes and spending are the subject of fiscal policy, whereas the financial markets, the availability of credit, money, and other financial assets are the subject of monetary policy. In order to track and affect a country's economy, the government must alter its level of spending and taxation through fiscal policy. It could be used in conjunction with monetary policy, which the central bank use to affect the amount of money in a country. To accomplish macroeconomic objectives in a country, these two policies are used. To put it another way, fiscal policy is a key tool for achieving economic stabilisation because it entails steps taken to regulate and control the scope, cost, and availability of economic activity as well as its direction in order to accomplish certain macroeconomic policy goals and buck harmful economic trends (Abdullah, 2016)

Government is an entity with a wide range of duties. The manners and patterns in which these functions are carried out, according to Medee and Nembee (2011), differ from society to society. There was a school of thought on economics that advocated a perfect state in the market system prior to the Great Depression of the 1930s. Say's Law, which argues that supply creates its own demand, is at the foundation of this theory. A laissez-faire economic system was created as a result of Say's ideas and Adams Smith's "invisible hand" self-correcting mechanism.

This economic structure was reversed as a result of the emergence of the great depression and the ensuing stock market collapses. However, Say's law was "appraised, faulted, and a new doctrine was

proposed based on the prescription of John M. Keynes" (Jumbo, 2010). Jumbo went on to say that Keynes' ideologies called for government action in an effort to stop the great depression and the ensuing economic crisis from becoming a full-fledged catastrophe. Over time, the government's involvement in macroeconomic operations has given rise to the notion of fiscal policy, which is the focus of this study. In order to achieve specific macroeconomic goals, including economic stability and growth, the government must manage its resources through fiscal policy, according to Jhinghan (2006). In general, it means raising money through taxes and using that money for development.

By means of the Lagos Treaty, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) was created on May 28th, 1975. The goal of the 15-member regional organisation ECOWAS is to advance economic integration across all sectors of the member nations' economies. Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Cote d'Ivoire, The Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Senegal, and Togo are the member nations that make up ECOWAS. ECOWAS was established to promote the objective of collective self-sufficiency for its member states and is regarded as one of the cornerstones of the African Economic Community. As a trading union, it also aims to unite all nations into a single, sizable trading bloc.

Industrial, transportation, telecommunications, energy, agricultural, natural resources, commerce, monetary and financial issues, as well as social and cultural issues, are all included in the area's planned integrated economic activity. Economic integration has long been a goal, and the regional organisation has made significant progress since the treaty's ratification, which provided it the necessary legal authority. According to recent evaluations, the regional organisation has surpassed the goals set by its founders. A toast to a feasible integration and successful regional coexistence, the organisation is now recognised on a global scale (Abdullah, 2016).

The goal of ECOWAS is to establish a region without borders where people may access the region's enormous resources and take advantage of them by creating opportunities in a healthy environment. ECOWAS has built an integrated area where people may move freely, have access to effective health and education systems, engage in economic and commercial activity, and live dignified lives in an environment of peace and security. ECOWAS is designed to be an area where democracy, the rule of law, and good governance are upheld.

In order to achieve economic integration, significant progress has been made in coordinating macroeconomic policies and the promotion of the private sector. The implementation of the roadmap for the ECOWAS single currency programme, monitoring and evaluating performance and macroeconomic convergence, management of the ECOWAS Macroeconomic Database and Multilateral Surveillance System (ECOMAC), and collaboration with other regional and international institutions are some initiatives that have resulted from these efforts (Appah, 2013).

Fiscal policy and its effects on economic growth have been hot topics in the nations of this West African sub-region over the past ten years. Others supported the effectiveness of monetary measures, while some supported the use of the public budget as a crucial tool for managing an economy. Therefore, Omitogun and Ayinla (2007) concluded that the utilisation of a public expenditure as a tool to govern an economy was its most important component. The implementation of fiscal policy frequently has its origins in the budget and has historically been linked to an increase in taxation and public spending to have an impact on economic activity. Fiscal policy is believed to undermine economic growth by distorting the impact of taxes and by wasting money on unnecessary government spending.

The effects of fiscal policy on growth have sparked a sizable amount of theoretical and empirical research. Increased government expenditure on physical and social infrastructure, as well as investment on health and education, is thought to accelerate the rate of expansion of national production, which is seen as one of a country's key macroeconomic goals. Road, power, communication, and rail infrastructure investments reduce production costs, increase private sector investment, and increase company profitability, all of which contribute to increased economic growth.

The debate regarding the effectiveness of fiscal policy as a tool for producing growth is still open due to the conflicting findings of earlier studies. There are two perspectives, according to Oshinowo (2015), on how government support for education, research and development, productive investment, law and order, and the delivery of public services might promote growth over the long and short terms. The second argument, on the other hand, contends that governments, particularly those in developed economies, are ineffective and bureaucratic, and that this causes them to hinder growth when they get engaged in the productive sectors of the economy. Fiscal policy is believed to disrupt the effects of taxation and inefficient government spending, which in turn disrupts economic progress. There are several theories regarding how fiscal policy affects the outcomes of economic performance. Supporters of the classical school of thought believed that government spending has a temporary and ineffective effect, particularly over the long term when prices adjust and output is at its highest, according to Khosravi and Karami (2010). In a similar vein, endogenous thinkers asserted that government spending and taxes have both short- and long-term effects on economic growth (Khosravi and Karami, 2010).

Over the years, the West African sub-region's economies have struggled with structural reform to suit the needs of 21st-century economies as well as growth and stability challenges. Despite the government's arsenal of fiscal and monetary policies, as well as a variety of growth theories and models, these economies have not been able to achieve sustained growth. They continue to suffer from internal instability and external shocks. Consequences of these oscillations include extreme unemployment, low income, high levels of inequality, and widespread poverty. Together, these characteristics either hinder economic growth or only benefit a few number of people who are in a position to benefit at the expense of the less fortunate. Fiscal policy still has a ways to go before it is used effectively to govern the economy, particularly in emerging nations like the West African subregion. But, there is a lot of embezzlement, poor management, and corruption. Public monies are frequently wasted, and certain expenditures have been politicised.

According to Okpanachi (2004), the region has experienced macroeconomic disequilibrium on occasion due to inappropriate government spending, unfavourable tax laws, and excessive deficits. The cyclical oscillations in the economies' operations have led to recurring increases in the unemployment and inflation rates of the countries, as well as external sector disequilibrium.

In order to achieve specific macroeconomic objectives and buck undesirable economic trends, fiscal policy, which is a key tool for stabilising the economy, entails actions to control and regulate the volume, cost, and availability of money in an economy as well as the direction of money. As a result, they cannot be left to market forces like supply and demand or other instruments of stability like monetary and exchange rate policy. Taxes, which are the cornerstone of fiscal policy, may rise or fall, as well as government spending, may be included in this. However, as neither of these tools can address every issue with the economy, government policies must combine fiscal and monetary policy tools to stabilise the economy.

Despite significant government investment in infrastructure and human capital development, the West African sub-region's countries have endured chronic poverty, high unemployment, poor infrastructure development, reliance on foreign technology, outlandish inflationary tendency, inadequate maintenance of infrastructure, and high debt loads for the past three decades.

Additionally, the region has experienced a steep decline in revenue and spending, an increase in the financing of deficits, and an unstable fiscal policy, primarily because of the global economic downturn. A decrease in government spending and eventual economic stagnation followed this. This has prevented the region from reaching its full potential for long-term economic growth and development. The economies of this region have consistently fallen short of expectations despite having abundant natural and human resources and a rising trend in public spending year after year. The question now is how application of fiscal policy measures has affected the economic growth in the west African sub region. As a result, this study aims to determine the impact of fiscal policy on the economic growth of five selected countries in the West African sub-region of Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Theoretical Literature

1. *The Keynesian Theory of Economic Growth (1936)*: In contrast to the idea of Say's law of market self-adjustment held by classical economists, the Keynesians developed John Maynard Keynes' principle of perpetual unemployment equilibrium, arguing that market economies are self-adjusting and do not require government intervention in the economy. Keynes only recognises that variations in savings and investments are to blame for changes in economic activity and employment in an economy and that forces of demand and supply are unable to produce full employment. As a result, Keynesians promoted the use of unrestricted policy tools by the government to intervene in the free enterprise sector and restore steady growth. Unrestricted policies, including taxation and government expenditure, are used to control the economy. As a result, in order to boost depressed economies, the government should raise expenditure and lower taxes in order to boost disposable income, which in turn boosts aggregate demand and growth.
2. *Rostow's Stages of Growth Theory*: W.W. Rostow is the author of this theory. He asserts that there are five (5) stages to a nation's development. These stages are:
 - i. In a traditional society, decisions about the economy are made based on custom, tradition, and duty.
 - ii. The phase that precedes the stage of take-off, characterised by improvements in agriculture, the abandonment of unethical culture, and the creation of an entrepreneurial class.
 - iii. The take-off stage, which is characterised by an increase in saving rates and the creation of leading industries that pull other industries along with them, enabling the realisation of rapid growth.
 - iv. The stage of drive to maturity, characterised by the coordination of the industrial revolution, in which the economy has reached a key minimum speed in the growth process and the other sectors have caught up to the leading sector.
 - v. When the economy is in this stage of high mass consumption, it is said to have reached its full potential and residents can enjoy a respectable level of living standards (Anyanfo, 1996).
3. *The Harrod-Domar Growth Model*: The growth process analyses of Harrod (1939) and Domar (1946) are whence this theory gets its name. It is a traditional Keynesian theory of economic expansion. According to the model, an economy's growth is favorably correlated with its savings ratio and negatively correlated with its capital-to-output ratio. It implies that an economy doesn't naturally experience balanced growth. It suggests that more investments in tangible capital are possible with higher savings rates. By enhancing a nation's ability to produce products and services, this investment can boost its overall growth. The capital-output ratio displays the

amount of capital required to produce an output that is equal to one dollar. It illustrates how effective employing machines is. Due to this efficiency, a lower capital-output ratio promotes greater economic growth because it requires fewer inputs to produce larger outputs. The Harrod-Domar model identifies three types of growth;

- i. **Warranted Growth:** This is the rate of growth over which there is neither an expansion nor a contraction of the economy. It is the entrepreneurial equilibrium, the course that, given the tendency to save, will keep the supply and demand for products and services in equilibrium. It represents an economy's income growth rate at its maximum potential.
 - ii. **Actual Growth:** This is the real annual growth rate of a nation's gross domestic product (GDP), which is defined by the capital-output and saving ratios. It displays cyclical fluctuations in the growth rate over the short term.
 - iii. **Natural Growth:** An economy needs this level of growth in order to maintain full employment. It is influenced by large-scale factors like population, technology, resources, and capital equipment. It is the rise in output at full employment as indicated by the rate of technical advancement and population growth.
4. *The Neo-Classical Endogenous Growth Theory:* According to this idea, internal processes produce economic growth directly from within the system. It argues that improving a country's human capital will spur economic growth since faster inventions and higher investments in human capital will increase productivity. It also calls for institutions in the public and private sectors to support innovation projects. According to this theory of growth, government policies ability to raise a country's growth rate if they lead to more intense competition in markets and help to stimulate product and process innovation.
- i. There are increasing returns to scale from capital investment especially in infrastructure and investment in education and health and telecommunications.
 - ii. Private sector investment in research & development is a key source of technological progress
 - iii. The protection of property rights and patents is essential to providing incentives for businesses and entrepreneurs to engage in research and development
 - iv. Investment in human capital is a vital component of growth
 - v. Government policy should encourage entrepreneurship as a means of creating new businesses and ultimately as an important source of new jobs, investment and further innovation. (Kenton (2018), Barro and Martin (1990))
5. *Wagner's Law:* Wagner's Law, formulated by the German political economist Wagner (1893), proposes a "law of increasing state activity" and associates government growth with industrialization and economic development. Wagner identified three main reasons for the expansion of state expenditure:
- i. As industrialization progresses, the public sector tends to supplant the private sector in various activities. Functions such as administration and protection become increasingly important, leading to an increase in state involvement.
 - ii. Governments are required to provide cultural and welfare services, including education, public health services, retirement pensions, food subsidies, assistance during natural disasters, environmental protection programs, and other welfare functions.
 - iii. Industrialization often gives rise to technological advancements and the emergence of large corporations that tend to monopolize markets. To counteract these effects, governments must intervene and provide social and merit goods through budgetary means.

Wagner argued that during the process of industrialization, as the real income per capita of a nation increases, the proportion of public expenditures in total expenditures also increases. He observed that public spending is an endogenous factor, determined by the growth of national income. Therefore, it is the national income that influences the level of public expenditure

6. *Peacock and Wiseman Theory:* Based on their analysis of public expenditure in England, Peacock and Wiseman (1947) gleaned important insight into the nature of the rise in public spending. They suggested that, contrary to Wagner's theory, the growth in public spending does not follow an organic process in which the population votes for ever-increasing social services, the government enjoys spending money, and people dislike higher taxes. They emphasised that significant conflicts and other large-scale disturbances will have displacement

consequences that will raise public spending and revenue to new levels. The government will fall short of revenue and there will be an upward revision of taxation. Initially, citizens will engender displeasure but later on will accept the new tax levels. Peacock and Wiseman viewed the period of displacement as reducing barriers that protect local autonomy and increasing the concentration power over public expenditure to the Central government. During the process of public expenditure centralization, the role of state activities tends to grow larger and larger which can be referred to the concentration process of increasing public sector activities.

B. Empirical Review

Over the years, a sizable number of empirical studies have been conducted in an effort to determine the effect that fiscal policy has on economic growth. The majority of these research have proven the existence of a connection between fiscal policy and economic growth. Some of them are nation-specific, while others are international. In this section of the work, we will analyse as many works as we can, both those that are country-specific and those that cross national boundaries, while taking into account the various techniques used, their outcomes and conclusions, and in some cases, the writers' recommendations.

Benos (2019) also investigated the relationship between fiscal policy and economic expansion. The goal of the study was to determine whether reallocating public funds could boost economic growth. He used data from fourteen (14) EU countries from 1990 to 2016 and the ordinary least squares approach in his research. The endogenous growth model is supported by the investigation's findings. It became clear that public investments in infrastructure, such as those for economic development and general public services, and the preservation of property rights, such as those for defence and public safety, have a favourable effect on economic growth. It also showed that growth is suppressed by distortionary taxation and that government spending on social protection, human capital-enhancing activities (such as education, health, housing, community amenities, environmental protection, recreation, and culture), and recreation does not significantly affect growth. The study also showed that spending on social protection, defence, and education by the government serves as a growth inducer. OLS was utilised in this instance, whereas panel regression analysis was used in our investigation. Additionally, the study's statistics were final as of 2016.

Iran's monetary and fiscal policies were examined by Khosravi and Karimi (2010) in relation to economic growth. For the analysis, they used the Autoregressive Distributive Lag using data from 1960 to 2006. The findings showed that government spending has a considerable beneficial impact on growth whereas exchange rate and inflation have negative effects. According to the findings, authorities should aim to lower inflation and exchange rates and should also locate a future point of equilibrium for government spending if they want to see sustained economic growth in Iran. Critique: While our study employed panel regression analysis of five nations, ARDL was applied here. Additionally, the study's statistics were final as of 2006.

Using annual data spanning the years 1977 to 2016, Sikiru and Umaru (2018) looked into the connection between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller method was used to look at the time series' unit roots, and the Engle-Granger method was then used to run the co-integration test. In order to account for short-run dynamics, they estimated error correction models. The co-integration test corroborated the overall findings, which show that productive spending had a beneficial impact on economic growth during the research period and that there is a long-term relationship between them. They advocated that the government start making such productive expenditures in order to increase economic growth

since they saw government spending on economic, health, and educational services as productive expenditures. In contrast to our study, which used panel regression analysis across five nations, this application of Engel and Granger regression analysis was criticised. Additionally, the study's statistics were final as of 2016.

Using panel data analysis, Funete (2018) examined the effects of public spending and taxation on the economic growth of 21 Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) nations from 1965 to 2015. The investigation's findings showed that fiscal policy has three major effects on economic growth. First, government investment in infrastructure and other assets directly promotes factor accumulation. Second, through lowering disposable income and the motivation to save, governmental spending has a tendency to displace private investment. Third, there is proof that government has a significant negative externality impact on the level of productivity. Once the pertinent distortions are taken into account, the calculations indicate that the effective cost of a \$1 public expenditure is approximately \$1.3. And this shows that large efficiency costs are created by taxes and government spending, which should be considered when making budgetary decisions. Criticism of the Fixed and Random Effect While pooled mean group panel regression analysis of five nations was employed for our study, panel regression analysis was applied here. Additionally, the study's statistics were final as of 2015.

In his research, Matthew (2017) used a vector autoregressive model to assess the impact of fiscal policy variables on economic growth in South Africa. He used government deficits, tax expenditures, government consumption expenditures, and gross fixed capital formation as study variables. The study was conducted from 1990 to 2014. He came to four important conclusions based on the findings. First, government spending on personal consumption has a large positive impact on economic expansion. Second, although gross fixed capital formation from the government also contributes to output growth, its effect is less significant than that of consumption expenditure. The amount of the deficit does not appear to have a substantial impact on growth outcomes, but tax receipts have a favorable impact on production growth as well. Comment: While our study used a Pooled Mean Group of panel regression analysis of five nations, this application of VAR regression analysis was criticized. Additionally, the study's statistics were final as of 2014.

Enache (2017) used time series data from 1992 to 2003 to conduct an analysis using the ordinary least squares approach in order to examine the relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Romania. Given that fiscal policy is not a primary source of growth, the data he got show that there is little correlation between fiscal policy and economic growth. But he came to the conclusion that the government may indirectly, through fiscal policy, affect economic growth. Review: OLS regression analysis was utilised here, however our work used Pooled Mean Group panel regression analysis across five nations. Additionally, the study's statistics were final as of 2003.

Using a vector autoregressive model, Nurudeen and Usman (2017) examined the effect of government spending on economic growth in Nigeria from 1970 to 2008. Their research showed that government spending on health, transportation, and communication actually promotes economic growth whereas spending on total capital, total recurrent, and education expenditures have the opposite effect. Comment: While our study used a Pooled Mean Group of panel regression analysis of five nations, this application of VAR regression analysis was criticised. Additionally, the study's statistics were final as of 2008.

Abdullah (2016) used OLS to examine the relationship between government spending and economic growth over the years 1980–2010 and found that the size of government spending has

a significant impact on how the economy performs. He continued by advising the government to increase budgetary spending on infrastructure, social programmes, and economic initiatives in addition to supporting and encouraging the private sector to grow more quickly. Review: OLS regression analysis was utilised here, however our work used Pooled Mean Group panel regression analysis across five nations. Additionally, the study's statistics were final as of 2010.

C. Theoretical framework

The Keynesian theory of economic growth, which emphasises the significance of government intervention in the economy, serves as the theoretical basis for this research. The Keynesians are the economists of the twentieth century who embraced and expanded John Maynard Keynes' theory of perpetual unemployment equilibrium, which runs counter to the notion of classical economists on Say's law of market, which claims that market economies are self-adjusting so there is no need for government involvement in the economy. The former is of the opinion that the most effective political tool for stabilising and advancing the economy is fiscal policy. Demand-side economists is another name for them. Keynes concedes that conditions of full employment could not be achieved by the forces of supply and demand.

Therefore, Keynesians believed that the free enterprise economy could only be brought out of a depression and ensure stable growth through government intervention (public sector) through the deployment of unlimited policy measures. Unrestricted policies, such as taxation and government spending, are employed to control the economy. According to Keynes, the government should increase expenditure in order to raise aggregate demand and subsequently, growth, in order to rectify a depressed economy.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Model Specification

The model for this study showed the effect of fiscal policy instruments on the economy of five selected countries of the ECOWAS sub-region.

The study was structured following the approach in Funete (2018) who using the fixed effect of panel data analysis investigated the impact of public expenditures and taxation on the economic growth of twenty-one Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries over a time frame of 1965 – 2015 in a model: $GDP_{it} = b_0 + b_1EXPINV_{it} + b_2EXPPROD_{it} + b_3TAXREV_{it} + U_{it}$. The investigation's findings showed that fiscal policy has three major effects on economic growth. First, government investment in infrastructure and other assets directly promotes factor accumulation. Second, through lowering disposable income and the motivation to save, governmental spending has a tendency to displace private investment. Third, there is proof that government has a significant negative externality impact on the level of productivity.

The model can be specified functionally below:

$$GRGDP = F(GNEXP, TAXRATE, EXT D) \quad (1)$$

These models could be linearly specified below:

$$GRGDP_{it} = b_0 + b_1GNEXP_{it} + b_2TAXRATE_{it} + b_3EXTD_{it} + U_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$b_1 > 0 \quad b_2 < 0 \quad b_3 > 0$$

Where:

GRGDP = Is the Growth Rate of Gross Domestic Product measured at Purchasing Power Parity of the selected five ECOWAS countries

GNEXP =Gross National expenditure of five ECOWAS countries

TAXRATE = Tax rate of the five ECOWAS countries

EXTD = External Debt

U_t = Error term

B. Sources of Data and Measurement

For its analysis, the study used secondary data. The data are balanced panel data because they combine cross-sectional data from five ECOWAS countries with time series data covering a 20-year period (2001 to 2020) from World Bank databases, Central Bank Reports of the countries, and IMF to create a balanced panel of 100 observations. The information includes that on:

- i. Growth rate of GDP-Definition: Annual percentage growth rate of GDP based on constant local currency prices and market prices. The basis for aggregates is constant 2010 US dollars. GDP is calculated as the total gross value added by all producers who are residents of the economy, plus any applicable product taxes, minus any unaccounted-for subsidies. It is estimated without taking into account the deterioration and depletion of natural resources or the depreciation of manufactured assets. The World Bank and OECD National Accounts data files were used as the data's primary sources.
- ii. Gross National Product (GNI) Expenditure as a percentage the total of general government final consumption spending (formerly known as general government consumption) and gross capital creation (previously known as gross domestic investment) is known as gross national expenditure (previously known as domestic absorption). The World Bank and OECD National Accounts data files were used as the data's primary sources.
- iii. Tax rate (% of commercial profit) - Definition: Total tax rate calculates the amount of taxes and required contributions that firms must pay as a percentage of their commercial earnings after taking into account allocable deductions and exemptions. Included are taxes that are deducted (such as personal income tax) or gathered and paid to taxing bodies (such as value-added taxes, sales taxes, or goods and service taxes). This information was obtained from the Doing Business project of the World Bank (<http://www.doingbusiness.org/>).
- iv. Total external debt stocks to gross domestic product is known as external debt (% of GNI). Total external debt is the sum of all loans to nonresidents that can be repaid with money, products, or services. The sum of all long-term debt, including that incurred with IMF assistance, short-term debt, and private debt that is not guaranteed by the government constitutes total external debt. All debt with an original maturity of one year or less is considered short-term debt, as is interest accrued on long-term debt. The Gross National Income (GNI, formerly GNP) is the total of all value added by resident producers, any product taxes (minus subsidies) that are not taken into account in valuing output, and net receipts of primary income (employee remuneration and property income from abroad). The World Bank's International Debt Statistics was the source of this information.

C. *The Pooled Mean Group Model and Mean Group model*

There are certain pertinent characteristics of the Pooled Mean Group Model (PMG) or Error Component Model (ECM). A clear problem with the least square dummy variable (LSDV) model is whether the dummy variable's inclusion and the resulting reduction in degrees of freedom are actually required. The covariance model was developed because, when defining the regression model, we neglected to include pertinent explanatory variables that do not change over time (and perhaps others that do change over time but have similar values for all cross-sectional units). The covariance model also developed because the use of dummy variables was an attempt to hide our ignorance. Thus, this ignorance is represented by the disturbance factor in the error components model or pooled mean group model. We can rewrite the model as;

$$GRGDP_{it} = b_0 + b_1GNPEXP_{it} + b_2TAXRATE_{it} + b_3EXTD_{it} + U_{it} \quad \text{-----}(3.3)$$

Instead of treating b_0 as fixed, it was assumed that it is a random variable with a mean value of b_0 . The intercept value for each of the five ECOWAS countries can be expressed as:

$$b_{0i} = b_0 + E_i \quad \text{-----}(3.4)$$

where E_i is a random error term with a mean value of zero and a variance of δ^2 .

What this suggests is that the five ECOWAS countries included in our sample are drawn from a number of countries of ECOWAS. The individual differences in the intercept values of all the five selected ECOWAS countries are reflected in the stochastic term E_i .

The overall equation is restated as;

$$GRGDP_{it} = b_0 + b_1GNPEXP_{it} + b_2TAXRATE_{it} + b_3EXTD_{it} + E_i + U_{it} \quad \text{-----}(3.5)$$

Where:

$$W_{it} = E_i + U_{it}$$

The composite error term W_{it} consists of two components; E_i , which is the cross-section, or individual-specific error component, and U_{it} , which is the combination of time series and cross-section error component and it varies over cross-section as well as time series. The error components model (ECM) is so mentioned because the composite error term is made up of two or more error components.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

A. *Descriptive Statistics of the Data Used in the Analysis*

Below is the summary of statistical analysis of the data for the variables used indicating the number of observations, mean and standard deviation of the overall data.

TABLE I
STATISTICS OF THE VARIABLES USED IN THE STUDY

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Observation
GRGDP Overall	5.301	4.910	-20.6	26.42	N=100
Between		0.630	4.647	6.237	n=5
Within		4.877	-20.792	26.227	T=20
GNEXP Overall	109.927	10.596	81.78	148.18	N=100
Between		9.150	95.324	120.559	n=5
Within		6.680	96.357	137.547	T=20
TAXRATOverall	92.711	98.488	25	285.9	N=100
Between		75.984	31.13	201.08	n=5
Within		70.952	-61.069	220.616	T=20
EXTD Overall	43.096	31.734	4.95	138.57	N=100
Between		19.596	15.366	59.35	n=5
Within		27.510	7.246	127.164	T=20

Source: Extract from computer printout of descriptive statistics using Stata 15

The table I above shows the descriptive statistics of data used in the analysis of the study. The overall mean of growth rate of Gross Domestic Product (GRGDP), Government capital expenditure (GNEXP) tax rate (TAXRATE) and External Debt (EXTD) are 5.301, 109.927, 92.711 and 43.096 respectively. The total number of observations is 100 obtained from the 5 selected countries of the ECOWAS for a time series period of 20 years. The maximum and minimum values of the variables with their standard deviation for the overall, between and within are shown on the table.

B. Correlation Matrix

TABLE II
CORRELATION MATRIX OF THE VARIABLES USED FOR THE STUDY

	LGDP	EXDT	EXDS
GRGDP	1.0000		
GNEXP	0.0319	1.0000	
TAXRATE	-0.0328	0.0933	1.0000
EXTD	0.0574	0.2893	0.4674

Source: Using Stata 15, extract descriptive statistics from a computer printout.

The correlation matrix's output displays the link between the variables studied. GNEXP and GRGDP have a positive association, whereas TAXRATE and GRGDP have a negative relationship. This is consistent with the a priori assumption.

Overall, there is no substantial link between the autonomous parameters, implying that covariance does not exist and therefore no multicollinearity.

C. Pre-Estimation Diagnostics

1. *Presentation of the Panel Unit root Results:* The Im Persaran-Shin (IPS) unit root test was employed to test for panel unit root for all the macroeconomic variables employed for the study. The results are presented on the table below:

TABLE III
PANEL UNIT ROOT TEST RESULT USING IM, PERSARAN-SHIN (IPS)

Variable	P-value@ level	t-statistic @first difference	P-value @1 st Difference	Critical value	Order of Integration
GRGDP	0.0000	t-bar = -5.743 t-tlde-bar= -3.003 z-t-tidle-bar= -4.820	0.0000	1% = -3.130 5% = -2.820 10%= -2.670	I(0)
GNEXP	0.0013	t-bar = -5.812 t-tlde-bar= -3.387 z-t-tidle-bar= -5.844	0.0002	1% = -3.130 5% = -2.820 10%= -2.670	I(0)
TAXRATE	0.6000	t-bar = -4.784 t-tlde-bar= -3.146 z-t-tidle-bar= -5.139	0.0000	1% = -3.130 5% = -2.820 10%= -2.670	I(1)
EXTD	0.6913	t-bar = -3.909 t-tlde-bar= -2.896 z-t-tidle-bar= -4.409	0.0000	1% = -3.130 5% = -2.820 10%= -2.670	I(1)

Source: Data regression extracted from a PC using Stata version 15

The Im Persaran-Shin (IPS) decision rule states that if the t-statistics is greater than the critical value at the 5% significance level and the probability value (P-Value) is less than 0.05, the variable is stationary at that level; otherwise, the difference is taken until the variable becomes stationary. The findings demonstrate that two of the variables studied were stationary at levels (GRGDP and GNEXP) while TAXRATE and EXTD were stationary at first difference. The reality that the factors were not all stationary at the same order of integration and to prevent misunderstanding bias that comes with evaluating co-integrated variables, the study used the Pedroni Panel Cointegration test to check for cointegration.

2. *Pedroni Panel Cointegration Test:* Following the result of the unit root tests presented in tables II above, the study carried out the cointegration test using the Pedroni Panel Cointegration test. The procedure is to obtain the test statistic of the components (v, rho, t and adf) for the panel and group, then identify which of the statistics is significant. If the probability is less than 0.05, then we conclude that the statistics is significant or otherwise

TABLE IV
PEDRONI PANEL TEST STATISTICS FOR THE COMPONENTS

Test Statistic	Panel	Group
V	-1.981	-
Rho	-0.4995	0.384
T	-5.955	-5.83
adf	-2.769	-1.699

Source: Extract from computer on regression of data using Stata version 15

Below is the summary of the probability result for the test statistics:

TABLE V
PEDRONI PANEL TEST STATISTICS FOR THE COMPONENTS

Test Statistics	Statistics	Prob(chi2)	Decision (5%)
Panel-v	-1.981	1.952	Insignificant
Panel-rho	-0.499	1.382	Insignificant
Panel-t	-5.955	1.994	Insignificant
Panel-ADF	2.769	0.046*	Significant
Group-rho	0.384	0.700	Insignificant
Group-t	-5.83	2	Insignificant
Group-ADF	-1.699	1.910	Insignificant

Source: Extract from computer on regression of data using Stata version 15

Decision Rule here is that if majority of the statistics (both Panel and Group categories) are significant, then we conclude that there exist a long run panel cointegration between the dependent and predicting variables; and vice versa. In the table V above, 6 out of 7 test statistics were not significant. This confirmed the nonexistence of cointegration (there exist no long run panel cointegration between the dependent and predicting variables)

D. Panel ARDL Regression Results

1. *Results of the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) Models:* The The results of the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) model are analyzed below preparatory to application of Hausman test to determine whether to use PMG model or Mean Group (MG) model in the analysis of the study.

TABLE VI
RESULTS OF POOLED MEAN GROUP (PMG) MODEL ANALYSIS OF GRGDP MODEL

Variable	Coefficient	Z-value	Prob Value
Long run			
LGEXP	3.917	3.09	0.002
LTAXRATE	0.211	2.99	0.003
LEXTD	0.008	0.09	0.927
Short run			
ECT	-0.312	-2.42	0.016
D-LGEXP	0.666	0.45	0.065
D-LTAXRATE	-5.930	-1.45	0.014
D-LEXTD	-0.598	-1.57	0.117
Prob>F = 0.0000			

Source: Extract from computer on regression of data using Stata version 15

The long run results from the PMG model in table VI shows that GEXP, TAXRATE and EXTD have positive relationship with GRGDP in the period of study. While GEXP and TAXRATE are significant determinant of GRGDP, EXTD is not a significant determinant of GRGDP.

In the short run of the PMG model in table VI shows that TAXRATE and EXTD have negative relationship with GRGDP while GEXP has a positive effect on GRGDP in the period of study. While GEXP and

TAXRATE are significant determinant of GRGDP, EXTD is not a significant determinant of GRGDP. The error term ECT is correctly signed and significant at 5%. The long run disequilibrium is corrected into short run equilibrium at a speed of 31.2%

Note that the decision rule is that if the probability value of a variable is less than 0.05 that is at 5% significance level and the Z-Value is greater than 1.96 critical value, it indicates that that variable is a significant determinant of the dependent variable otherwise it is not a significant determinant of the dependent variable. If the value of the coefficient is negative it signifies inverse relationship and vice versa. The Prob>F is 0.0000 which indicates that the model is significant.

2. *Results of the Mean Group (MG) Model:* Following the result of the unit root tests presented in tables II above, the study carried out the cointegration test using the Pedroni Panel Cointegration test. The procedure is to obtain the test statistic of the components (ν , ρ , t and adf) for the panel and group, then identify which of the statistics is significant. If the probability is less than 0.05, then we conclude that the statistics is significant or otherwise

TABLE VII
RESULTS OF MEAN GROUP (MG) MODEL ANALYSIS OF GRGDP MODEL

Variable	Coefficient	Z-value	Prob Value
Long run			
LGNEXP	2.160	0.74	0.457
LTAXRATE	-8.068	-4.35	0.000
LEXTD	-0.594	2.53	0.012
Short run			
ECT	-1.055	-4.44	0.000
D-LGNEXP	-1.149	-0.58	0.562
D-LTAXRATE	1.196	0.29	0.768
D-LEXTD	0.399	0.93	0.355
Prob>F = 0.0000			

Source: Extract from computer on regression of data using Stata version 15

The F- probability of F value of 0.000 suggests that the model is significant at 5% significance level. The long run results from the MG model in table VII shows that TAXRATE and EXTD have negative relationship with GRGDP and GNEXP has positive relationship in the period of study. While EXTD and TAXRATE are significant determinant of GRGDP, GNEXP is not a significant determinant of GRGDP.

In the short run of the model in table VII shows that TAXRATE and EXTD have positive relationship with GRGDP while GNEXP has a negative effect on GRGDP in the period of study. In the short run of the MG model, none of the variables is a significant determinant of GRGDP. The error term ECT is correctly signed and significant at 5%. The long run disequilibrium is corrected into short run equilibrium at a speed of 105.5%

3. *The Hausman Testt:* In statistics, the normality tests are used in order to determine whether a given set of data is well-defined by a normal distribution. Histogram of residuals and the Jarque–Bera test were used to determine normality. Figure 1 showed that Jarque-Bera statistic had a P-value of 0.047239 implying that the probability is less than 5% therefore the data were normally distributed.

TABLE VIII
RESULTS OF HAUSMAN TEST OF PMG AND MG OF THE MODEL

Variable	PMG Coefficient	MG Coefficient	Difference
LGNEXP	3.917	3.914	-0.002
LTAXRATE	0.211	-2.696	-2.907
LEXTD	0.008	-0.185	-0.194

$$\text{Chi2}(3) = 2.08$$

$$\text{Prob}>\text{chi2} = 0.5565$$

Source: Extract from computer on regression of data using Stata version 15

The study employed the Hausman specification test to determine whether to use the pooled mean group model or the mean group model.

It is a test of hypothesis of the coefficients whether they are systematic or otherwise. If the probability chi-squares of the model are less than 0.05 that is at 5% significance level the null hypothesis is rejected suggesting the use of mean group (MG) model or otherwise the pooled mean group (PMG) model is adopted.

The results of the Hausman specification test in table VIII above shows that the probability chi square is 0.5565 hence insignificant and so we accept the null hypothesis of 'difference in coefficients not systematic' and conclude to use the PMG model for analysis of this study.

4. *Test for Cross Sectional Dependence/Contemporaneous Correlation:* The test for cross sectional dependence or contemporaneous correlation is more of an issue in macro panels with long time series over 20-30 years. However, the test was carried out using the Pesaran Test and the Pesaran's test of cross-sectional independence is 4.104 with Pr of 0.0000. The Average absolute value of the off-diagonal elements is 0.372. These results indicated the independence of the countries in terms of data behaviour.
5. *Test for Autocorrelation:* The Wooldridge test for autocorrelation was carried out and the result indicated the existence of no first order serial correlation with the $\text{prob}>F$ of 0.4541.
6. *Test Heteroscedasticity:* The Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for Heteroscedasticity was carried out and the result show that the $\text{prob}>\text{chibar2}$ of 0.4305 greater than 5% significant value indicate absence of Heteroscedasticity

TABLE IX
VARIANCE INFLATION FACTOR (VIF)

VARIABLES	VIF	1/VIF
LGNEXP	1.64	0.4078
LTAXRATE	1.35	0.4263
LEXTD	1.26	0.4317
MEAN VIF	1.41	

Source: Extract from computer on regression of data using Stata version 15.

E. Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study indicated the existence of no cointegration that is no long run relationship exists among the variables of the study hence the short run PMG model in table VI is used in the analysis. The short run of the PMG model shows that TAXRATE and EXTD have negative relationship with GRGDP while GNEXP has a positive effect on GRGDP in the period of study. While GNEXP and TAXRATE are significant determinant of GRGDP, EXTD is not a significant determinant of GRGDP. These results conformed with apriori and in line with the findings in Funete (2018), Benos (2019) and Sikiru & Umaru 2018.

The implication of these findings is that appropriate government capital expenditure channeled on productive sectors such as education, health, and economic services will boost economic growth in the selected ECOWAS countries.

The findings also suggested that inappropriate taxation and excessive borrowing acted as a disincentive to growth in the region in the period under consideration since taxation and external

debt have negative relationship with economic growth rate. These results confirmed the findings in Funete (2018).

The error term ECT is correctly signed and significant at 5%. The long run disequilibrium is corrected into short run equilibrium at a speed of 31.2%

. The Prob>F is 0.0000 which indicated that the model is significant.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Concluding Remark

The role of fiscal policy in economic stabilization and growth in any economy cannot be overemphasized. This research sets to investigate empirically the relationship between fiscal policy measures and economic growth in five selected ECOWAS countries from 2001 - 2020.

The study shows that over the years, government's expenditure and tax are viable fiscal measures that influenced economic growth in the sub region. When the government of the selected countries wants to stimulate growth in the economy, it increases her expenditure on investment activities and reduces taxes. Most often, their budget deficits are financed through external borrowing.

Government financial operations are well-nigh impossible without taxation. Apart from this, taxation can be a powerful means in order to achieve the goals of social progress and the objectives of economic development. It serves as a device to encourage the growth of certain activities by way of giving exemptions, discourage use of certain products by way of imposing heavier charges like those sin taxes which are imposed upon tobacco products, or strengthen anemic enterprises, also by way of tax exemptions. Local industries may be protected through taxation by imposing high customs duties to foreign goods. Moreover, taxation can also be used to reduce inequities or inequalities in wealth and income by progressively higher taxes as in the case of estate and income tax

B. Recommendations

The study led to several findings and therefore several policy implications as well as recommendations are discussed below:

Since the findings of this study indicated that increased government spending lead to increased growth rate, appropriate government capital expenditure channeled on productive sectors such as education, health, and economic services will boost economic growth in the selected ECOWAS countries.

Based on the findings also, appropriate tax rate and tax base should be reviewed to increase tax revenue necessary for funding government expenditure instead of relying on external borrowing to finance budget deficits in the selected ECOWAS countries.

Government in the ECOWAS countries should source for other means of financing their budget deficits since excessive external borrowing acted as a disincentive to growth in the region in the period under consideration.

REFERENCES

1. Abata, M. A. and Essi, S. A. (2012). Fiscal/monetary policy and economic growth in Nigeria: A theoretical exploration. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 1(5), 75-98
2. Abata, J.M., Falade, V.B. and Onwe, J.T (2019). Fiscal policy and growth of the Nigerian economy: An empirical perspective Ibadan: *NISER Monograph Series* (3)
3. Abdulsalam S. A. and Abdullahi B. (2016). The impact of unemployment and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Economic Sciences Applied Research (IJBESAR)*, ISSN 2408-0101, Eastern Macedonia and Thrace Institute of Technology, Kavala, 9(1), 47-55
4. Abdullah, H. A. (2016). The relationship between government expenditure and economic growth in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of administrative science*, 12(2),173-191
5. Aigbokhan, B.E. (1998). Poverty growth and inequality in Nigeria: A case study. Final Report Submitted to the *African Economic Research Consortium*.
6. Ajie, H. A., Akekere, J. and Ewubare D. B. (2008). *Financial Institutions: Market and Contemporary Issues*. Port Harcourt. Pearl Publishers
7. Ajiobenebo, T. J. (2017). *Public Sector Economics: Principles, Theories, Issues and Applications. (3rd Ed.)* Port Harcourt: Lima Computers.
8. Ajisafe, R. A., and Folorunso, B. A. (2002). The relative effectiveness of fiscal and monetary policy in macroeconomic management in Nigeria. *The African Economic and Business Review*, 3(1), 23-40.
9. Akpakpan, E. B. (2014). *How to save the naira in Nigeria, Macroeconomics Action*. Abak.
10. Belpot Nig. Co.
11. Amanja, S. and Morrissey, P. (2005). Fiscal policy and economic growth in Kenya. *Publication by Centre for Research in Economic Development and International Trade*, University of Nottingham No. 05/06
12. Anyanfo, A.M.O., (1996). Public finance in a developing economy: The Nigerian Case. *Department of Banking and Finance*, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus, Enugu
13. Anyanwu, J. C. (1993). *Monetary economics: Theory, policy, and institutions*: Onitsha. Hybrid Publishers Ltd.
14. Appah B.C. (2013): *Fiscal economics theory*. Policy and institutions. Onitsha, Hybrid Publishers Ltd.
15. Aregbeyen, O. (2007). Public expenditure and economic growth in Africa. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 14(1): 1-25. Hybrid Publishers Nigeria Ltd.
- 16.
17. Arellano, M. and Bond, S. (1991) Some tests of specification for panel data: Monte Carlo evidence and an application to employment equations, *The Review of Economic Studies*, 58(2), 77–297
18. Bakare, A. S. (2017). Assessing the role of public spending for sustainable growth: Empirical analysis. *Journal of International Finance*, 3(2), 25-30.
19. Benos, N. (2019). Fiscal Policy and Economic Growth: Empirical Evidence from EU Countries. *Journal of Economic Surveys* 17(3):397 - 418
20. Bhartia, H.L., (2009) *Public Finance*. 14th Edition, New Delhi, India. Vikas Publishing House.
21. Bondunrin A.C, (2017): Notes on effect of fiscal and monetary policy on economic growth in Nigeria. *Accounting. Journal of Economic Growth* 4(2), 119-137.
22. Burrow P. and Hitiris T. (1974) *Macroeconomic Theory: A Mathematical Introduction*. Chichester. John Willey and Sons
23. Central Bank of Nigeria Report (2011): Fiscal Policy and Government Finance. *Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Report*.
24. Central Bank of Nigeria (2018). Fiscal Policy and Government Finance. *Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Report*.
25. Challis, R.E. and Kitney, R.I. (1991) *Biomedical signal processing (in four parts). Part 3*. The power spectrum and coherence function. *Medical & Biological Engineering & Computing*, 29, 225-241. doi:10.1007/BF02446704
26. Chowdhury, A.R. (1986). Monetary and fiscal impacts on economic activities in Bangladesh A note. *The Bangladesh Development Studies*. 14(2): 101-106.
27. Danjuma, I., Jubrin, S. M., and Blessing, S. E. (2012). An assessment of the effectiveness of fiscal policy in combating inflation pressure on the Nigerian Economy. *Erudit Journal of Business Administration and Management*, 1(1), 7-16.
28. Danmola, R. A., Olateju, A. O. & Abba, M. W. (2013). Nexus between public expenditure and economic growth by testing Wagner's law time series: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 2(4), 111-126
29. Dar, Atul and AmirKhalkhali, Sal. (2012). On the relation between regulation and economic growth. *International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER)*. 11(4), 126-147. 10.19030/iber.v11i2.6768.
30. Dauda, R. O. (2010). Investment in education and economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical evidence. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 55(3), 158-169.
31. Dormar E. (1946). Capital expansion, rate of growth, and employment. *Econometrica*, 14(2), 137-147. Published by *The Econometric Society*
32. Dominance, Third annual monetary policy conference proceedings on issues in fiscal (1970 - 1998). *The Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*, 42(1), 37-54
33. Dornbusch, R. and Fischer, S. (2010). *Macroeconomic* (5th ed.) New York: McGraw-Hill Publishing Company.
34. Ebimobowei, A. (2010). The relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria (1991 - 2005). *International Journal of Economic Development Research and Investment*1(2&3)
35. Eboigbe, S. & Idolor, E. J. (2013). External debt and public sector investment: The Nigerian perspective. *Journal of Accounting and Contemporary Studies*, 2(1), 7 – 16.
36. Ekpo, A. (1994). *Public expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria 1960 to 1992*: Final Report. Nairobi: AERC.
37. Ezeoha, A and Uche, C (2010). Rethinking monetary and fiscal policies in Nigeria.
38. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 2(1), 7 – 16.
39. Fadare, S.O. (2010). Recent banking sector reforms and economic growth in Nigeria. *Middle Eastern Finance and Economics*. 8(6), 1450-2889
40. Folorunso, B.A and Abiola, A.G. (2000): The long-run determinants of inflation in Nigeria.
41. *Nigeria Journal Economics and Social Studies*, 42(1), 10-26.
- 42.

43. Fu, D., Taylor, L.L. and Yucel, M.K. (2003). Fiscal policy and growth. Federal Reserve Bank
44. of Dallas Research Department Working Paper 0301. Dallas: Federal Reserve Bank. *Journal of Economics Literature*
45. Glyn, A. (1987). "Marxist economics". The New Palgrave: A Dictionary of Economics. 39095.
46. Gregoriou, A. And Ghosh S. (2007). The impact of government expenditure on growth: Empirical evidence from heterogeneous panel. Accessed from [Http://Www.Brunel.Ac.Uk/9379/Efwps/0701.Pdf]
47. Gujarati, D.N. (2004) *Basic Econometrics*. 4th Edition, Delhi. McGraw-Hill Companies.
48. Ihendinihu, J.U., Jones, E. & Ibanichuka, E.A. (2014). Assessment of the long- run equilibrium relationship between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria: 1986 to 2012". *The SIJ Transactions on Industrial, Financial & Business Management (IFBM)*, 6(1), 17 – 36..
49. Imoisi, A S. (2011). Problems surrounding the procedures of fiscal policy and its influence on economic growth. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3(1), 1348-1361.
50. Imoisi, A. Ilegbinosa, (2013). An Appraisal of Fiscal Policy Measures and its Implication for growth of the Nigerian Economy: 1970-2009, *Advances in Management & Applied Economics*, vol. 3, no.4, 2013, 193-204 ISSN: 1792-7544 (print version), 1792-7552(online) Science Press Ltd.
51. International Monetary Fund (2017). Guidance note on the bank-fund debt Sustainability framework for low income countries. <https://www.worldbank.org/content/dam/LIC%20DSF/Site%20File/assets/documentation/pp122617guidance-note-on-lic-dsf.pdf>
52. Iyoha, M. A., Oyefusi, S. A. & Oriakhi, D. E. (2003). *An Introduction to Modern*
53. *Macroeconomics*. Benin City: Mindex.
54. Jhingan, M.L. (2004) *Money, Banking, International Trade, and Public Finance*. 7th Edition, New Delhi. Vrinda Publication (P) Ltd.,
55. Jhingan, M. L. (2006). *Macroeconomic Theory*. New Delhi: Vrinda Publishers.
56. Jhingan, M. L. (2010). *Principles of Economics*. New Delhi: Vrinda Publishers.
57. Keynes, J. M. (1936). *The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money*. London: Cambridge University and Macmillan Press.
58. Khosravi, A. and Karimi, M. S. (2010). To investigate the relationship between monetary policy, fiscal policy and economic growth in Iran: Autoregressive distributed lag approach to cointegration. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 7(3), 420 - 424.
59. Kimberly, N. (2019). Public spending and economic growth during economic crises. *Southwestern Economic Review*, 4(1), 59–68.
60. Mahmood, A.M. and Sial, S.A (2012). Impact of fiscal policy and monetary policy on economic growth with an emphasis on intermediary role of technology: Time series evidence from Pakistan. *Africa Journal of Business Management*, 6(3), 280- 285.
61. Mansouri, B. (2008). Fiscal policy and economic growth: Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia compared. Proceeding in UNECA Conference on Macroeconomic Policy, Productive Capacity and Economic Growth in Africa. Addis Ababa, 23-25
62. Meedee, P.N. & Nembee, S.G (2011). Government expenditure and economic development: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(9), 18 -28.
63. Musgrave, R. A. and Musgrave, P. B. (1979). *Public Finance in Theory and Practice*. 2nd Edition. Kogakusha Tokyo. McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd
64. Nathan, P. (2012). The impact of fiscal policy on the Nigerian economy. *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4(1), 142-150.
65. Newbold, S. and Granger, P. (1974). Spurious regressions in econometrics. *Journal of Econometrics* 2(1), 111-120.
66. Nkiru, S. and Daniel, N. (2013). Impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(4), .64 -71.
67. Noman, R.M and Khuri W. T (2015). Meta-analysis of the effect of fiscal policy on economic growth in Bangladesh 1979-2013. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 20(4), 91-124.
68. Nurudeen, S. & Usman, A. (2010). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria. A disaggregated analysis. *Business and Economics Journal*, 4(1), 1-11.
69. Nworji, L. O. (2012). Effect of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria: A disaggregated time-series analysis. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*. 1(7), 2226-8235
70. Ogbole, F., Sonny, N. & Isaac, D. (2011). Fiscal policy: its impact on economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*, 3(6), 407-452.
71. Ogbole, O.F; Amadi, S.N and Isaac, I.D. (2013). The Relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria 1981 to 2010. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*. 3(6):407-417.
72. Ogege T.J. and Shiro S. D. (2012). The dynamics of Nigeria's monetary and fiscal policies in Nigeria, *Central Bank of Nigeria Publications*, 4(3), 11-12.
73. Ojo, M. O. (1992). Monetary policy in Nigeria in the 1980s and prospects in the 1990s. *CBN Economic and Financial Review*, 30(1), 11-12. Retrieved from http://www.valuefronteiraonline.com/public_upload/file/Wp68.pdf
74. Okpanachi, U.M. (2004). *Public Options for Repositioning the Nigerian Agricultural sector*
75. in the food Basket Myth.: Implication for Food Security and Agricultural policy in Nigeria, (ED). Aboki publishers.
76. Omitogun, O and Ayinla, T.A (2007). Fiscal policy and Nigerian economic growth. *Journal of Research in National Development*, 4(5), 5-20.
77. Omodero, A.C., Ihendinihu, J.U, and Azubuike, T.S. (2016). The effect of government expenditure on economic growth and development in developing countries: Nigeria as a case study. Lagos, *Central Bank of Nigeria Publications*, 4(3), 11-12
78. Osinowo H, (2015). Effect of fiscal policy on sectoral output growth in Nigeria *Journal of Advance in Economics and Business*, 3(2), 195-203
79. Otto, E. (2021). Fiscal policy in India. Ramanujan College, Delhi University., *International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research*, 6(4), 5-20.
80. Ozougwo, F.O. (2012). Fiscal policy and macroeconomic performance in Nigeria. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Department of Banking and Finance, Rivers State University of Science and Technology, Port Harcourt.
81. Peacock and Wiseman UK Essays. (2018). *Review Of Theories On Government Expenditure Economics Essay*. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/economics/review-of-theories-on-government-expenditure-economics-essay.php?vref=1>
82. Peter, S. M. & Simeon, F. (2019). Unconventional fiscal policy tools: a cross-country analysis. Committee on the Global Financial System (CGFS No. 63), *Bank for International Settlements*,
83. Philips, A.O. (1997): Nigerian fiscal policy, 1998 -2010. *Nigerian Institute of Social Economic Research (NISER)*, Monograph Series (17).
84. Robert M. S. and Trevor, U.. (2018). *Understanding The Growth Theory*
85. By Solow Economics Essay.

86. <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/economics/understanding-the-growth-theory-by-solow-economics-essay.php?vref=1>
87. Roy, F. H. (1939) An essay in dynamic theory. *The Economic Journal*, 49(193)
88. 14-33. Published by: Blackwell Publishing for the Royal Economic Society
89. Samson O., Abbas, A. Shiro, S. (2002), The dynamics of monetary and fiscal policy as a tool for economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*; 2(2), 71- 79. Published by Canadian Center of Science and Education.
90. Sikiru, J. B. And Umaru A. (2018) Fiscal policy and economic growth relationship in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 2(17), 81- 109.
91. Simorangkir, J. M. and Adamanti D.T. (2010). Fiscal and monetary policy: Economic effects. *Congressional Research Service (CSR) Report*, 3(2), 195-203.
92. Smith, A. (1776). *An inquiry into the wealth of nations*. Published in 1776.
93. Sulaiman, L. A. &Azeez, B. A. (2012). Effect of external debt on economic growth of Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 3(8), 71- 79.
94. Taiwo, A. S. &Agbatogun, K. K. (2011). Government expenditure in Nigeria: A sine qua non for economic growth and development. *Journal of Economic and Management*, 9(2), 1596 – 8308.
95. Valmont, B. (2006). Understanding Fiscal Policy. *Central Bank of Seycheles Quarterly Review*, 24(2), 71- 79. Accessed On 28th May, 2017 From [Www.Cenbankseychesles.Org](http://www.Cenbankseychesles.Org).
96. Yesufu, T. M. (2016). The Nigerian economy: Growth without development. *The Journal of University of Benin Social Science Series for Africa*, 4(7), 91- 119.
97. World Bank. (2002). Building Institutions for Markets. World Development Report. *New York. Oxford University Press*.